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HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF USING CHATGPT FOR DESIGNING ENGLISH READING COMPREHENSION TESTS FOR TENTH-GRADE STUDENTS

Hoang Hong Phuong¹, Le Thi Ha Quynh²

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ABSTRACT

Reading tests are effective assessments to evaluate EFL learners' reading ability; however, designing them has been reported by teachers to be time-consuming and demanding. With the development of AI tools like ChatGPT, many English teachers have employed them to assist in making such tests. While ChatGPT can support the generation of many reading test components, some concern that its created content is not reliable without human supervision. To investigate high school teachers' perceptions of using ChatGPT for this purpose, we carried out this study using embedded mixed-methods research. We distributed questionnaires to 20 high school teachers who were generally familiar with the tool; then, to gain an in-depth understanding of their opinions, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 10 randomly selected participants. After analyzing the data, we found that between 60% and 95% of the teachers agreed ChatGPT is useful in generating reading tests across various aspects, particularly in generating comprehension questions (95%) and saving time and effort (85%). However, 75% of respondents also recognized that certain issues persist in ChatGPT's output, such as repetitive or mechanical phrasing in questions, inconsistencies in passage length and structure, and potential inaccuracies or biases. This highlights the crucial role of teachers in reviewing and refining AI-generated content to ensure its suitability before using it in assessments.

Keywords: *ChatGPT in EFL/ ELT, English High School Teachers' perceptions, English Language Assessment.*

1. INTRODUCTION

ChatGPT is an artificial intelligence (AI) tool that allows users to ask it any questions and then provide them with human-like replies (Gregersen, 2024). It plays an important part in many sectors; especially in technical and education industries, with an estimate of 251 and 209 organizations using it in 2023 respectively, compared to about 100 organizations in other fields (Statista, 2023). According to AIPRM (n.d.), the top three most popular activities that users employ ChatGPT belong to education and office-based tasks, including writing extended prose, writing emails and letters, and creative writing. It is noticeable that organizations in the education sector are most likely to take advantage of ChatGPT as it benefits both educators and students in the teaching and learning process (Hong, 2023).

For learners, ChatGPT is employed as a virtual language tutor to enhance their language skills. Anggeraja et al. (2024) stated that when students do not understand the requirements of a writing task, they can ask ChatGPT to explain or to outline what they should do for that task. This AI tool, then, not only simulates real-life conversations but also provides students with useful responses.

In addition, after finishing an essay, students can request it to analyze their writing styles; provide feedback on content, organization, grammar, punctuation, spelling errors, etc.; and suggest a series of improvements (Konhke et al., 2023). Moreover, Abas et al. (2023) claim that ChatGPT is able to create a personalized learning experience for students by producing instant feedback, adapting to suit their needs, and creating interactive and engaging experiences.

For teachers, ChatGPT can help improve productivity and enhance teaching effectiveness. For example, it can assist teachers in evaluating students' performance by simplifying the assessment process, which reduces the teachers' workload and saves their time and energy (Koraishi, 2023). In addition, it supports educators in making lesson plans and producing learning materials aligning with specific themes, objectives, and learning needs by suggesting various aspects of teaching methods and innovative solutions (Karakas & Yesilyurt, 2023). Educators can also use this application to produce language test items, such as comprehension questions and writing prompts that suit learners' contexts and proficiency levels (Bonner et al., 2023).

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In terms of designing English language assessments like reading tests, ChatGPT is truly a powerful tool that can assist teachers in doing the task without spending much time thinking and adjusting them meticulously (Shin & Lee, J., 2023). It can generate specific test task components from searching materials, summarizing information, to creating reading texts and questions (Bezirhan & Davier, 2023; Sihite et al., 2023; Rivera-Rosas et al., 2024). In addition, factors that might influence readers' mindset and reduce test reliability, such as subjective judgments or biases can be avoided in AI-generated tests (UNESCO, 2023). However, this organization also mentions that AI can scale bias, as AI is developed on data, and if there are bias in the data itself, it can lead to unfair outcomes. Moreover, users of AI-powered reading comprehension test designs may also encounter some other challenges. Tseng and Warschauer (2023) state that AI tools like ChatGPT tend to drift off topic, provide improper content or simply hallucinate if it is not guided under human supervision. Meanwhile, findings from studies conducted by Nguyen (2023) and Negro (2024) reveal that the levels of difficulty of ChatGPT-generated passages and questions vary; they are too complicated for pre-intermediate students but too easy for learners with higher levels of English proficiency. This raises questions about the reliability and validity of such assessments if they are not revised by human experts.

In short, using ChatGPT to create English reading tests can bring educators both advantages and disadvantages. While numerous studies deeply delve into teachers' perceptions of using ChatGPT for this task at higher education levels, research on high school teachers remains rare. In expecting to contribute more empirical observations in the research field, we conduct this study based on two research questions:

1. Do high school teachers think ChatGPT can assist them in designing English reading tests for grade 10 students? If so, to what extent do they utilize ChatGPT for this purpose?
2. What are teachers' concerns when using ChatGPT to design English reading tests for grade 10 students?

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The research mainly focuses on English high school teachers' perceptions of using ChatGPT version 4.0 in designing reading tests for 10th-grade students. To carry out this research, we

employed an embedded mixed-methods research approach (quantitative and qualitative) to examine the opinions of 20 high school English teachers (18 females and 2 males) from various high schools in Daklak Province on this matter. The age of the participants ranges from 24 to 42, with an average age of 31. They have at least two years of English teaching experience, with 70% having more than five years. Additionally, 95% of them are familiar with and confident in integrating ChatGPT into language teaching, but they had rarely used this AI tool for English language learning prior to becoming English teachers. 60% use this AI tool regularly to create reading tests, while the rest use it occasionally. However, only 30% of the respondents stated that they had received formal training in the use of ChatGPT or similar AI tools, such as workshops conducted by RMIT University, for teaching purposes. The remaining respondents said that their use of the application largely depends on personal experience and discussions with colleagues.

2.2. Methods

The study was conducted at the beginning of 2025 and split into two phases: Phase 1. Questionnaires, which involved collecting quantitative data from high school English teachers (20-26 Jan, 2025), and Phase 2. Semi-Structured Interviews, qualitative insights were gathered to complement the survey findings (03-09 Feb, 2025). In the first phase, the participants are required to complete questionnaires via Google Docs. The questionnaire includes 30 questions covering the respondents' background information, perceptions and experiences of using this application. In the second phase, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 10 randomly selected participants from the original 20 who completed the questionnaire in Phase 1. The interview questions were partly based on those used in the questionnaire, but were refined to focus on key findings that emerged from the initial data analysis. The aim was to explore whether the interviewees shared similar views with the highlighted results and to understand the reasons behind their responses. Each interview lasted approximately 9 minutes on average and was audio-recorded for subsequent qualitative analysis to complement the questionnaire data. For privacy, their identities are kept anonymous and they are named V1 to V10.

The quantitative data collected from the questionnaires is analyzed through descriptive statistics. The analysis aimed to reveal whether the

participants believed that ChatGPT could assist them in creating English reading tests for 10th-grade students, and to what extent they used the tool for this purpose. In addition, it would figure out potential challenges that the respondents might encounter when using this AI tool in making such tests. The questionnaires were delivered to the participants on 20 Jan, 2025; and the response rate was 100%, with all the participants completing the questionnaire. Meanwhile, the semi-structured interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams or Google Meet, depending on which application was available to the participants. The qualitative data obtained from the interviews would be analyzed to gain information that support the results from the questionnaires. This analysis helps us have a deeper understanding of how participants use ChatGPT to create reading tests for tenth graders, their perceptions of this application, the specific challenges they might face, and their recommendation for further research.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Teachers Specific Uses of ChatGPT in Reading Test Design

To gain deeper insight into specific tasks where ChatGPT could help high school teachers in English reading test design, we included 10 different statements in the questionnaires, which are presented in Table 3.1. Accordingly, teachers

reported using ChatGPT to support various components of English reading test creation, such as generating reading passages, paraphrasing texts, producing multiple-choice or True/False questions. Notably, all participants (100%) indicated a strong preference for using ChatGPT to generate multiple-choice questions based on provided texts. Meanwhile, the response rates for checking the accuracy and organization of self-created texts and for generating both texts and corresponding questions were significantly lower, at only 45% and 55%, respectively. The percentage of remaining tasks is fairly evenly distributed, ranging from 70% to 85%. The data possibly indicate that teachers mainly use ChatGPT to modify the content of the test including both texts and questions and to generate questions.

These results were consistent with most of the responds received in the interviews. For example, V4 and V8 noted that they no longer spend hours choosing texts or paraphrasing provided texts to adjust readability, instead, they just ask ChatGPT to generate them. Besides these uses, V3 and V7 utilize ChatGPT for other tasks, such as generating passages based on some given words that students have learned in a specific lesson to make 15-minute classroom quizzes, while V5 employs this AI tool to assist her in finding reading texts quickly from different sources.

Table 3.1. Teachers Specific Uses of ChatGPT in Reading Test Design

	Responses from participants	
	Total	Percentage
Paraphrasing provided texts to adjust readability	17	85%
Paraphrasing provided texts to meet a word count limit	16	80%
Generating texts according to a particular topic	15	75%
Checking the accuracy and organization of texts that you create yourself	9	45%
Paraphrasing provided questions to adjust readability	17	85%
Paraphrasing provided questions to meet a word limit	14	70%
Generating multiple-choice questions based on provided texts	20	100%
Generating True/False questions based on provided texts	16	80%
Generating both texts and corresponding questions	11	55%

3.2. Teachers' Perceptions of ChatGPT's Utility in Reading Test Design

3.2.1. Teachers Evaluation of ChatGPT's Ability to Generating Reading Test Content

Table 3.2.1. shows how English teachers evaluated ChatGPT-generated reading test content by giving scores on a scale of 1 (very poor) to 5 (very good). As illustrated in the table, in most

cases, teachers recognized this AI tool's ability at moderate (score 3 on the scale). Significantly, 50% of teachers rated its ability to generate accurate texts in terms of grammar, word choices, and overall appropriateness as high, giving it a score of 4. Similarly, the accuracy and variety of ChatGPT-generated texts were also rated at this score, with percentages ranging from 40% to 45%. However, scores for the naturalness of generated questions

and the ability to adjust text length and structure showed the greatest variation, ratings ranged from 1 to 5. This suggests that while this application generally produces accurate texts and questions, it might be inconsistent in generating natural questions and adjusting text length and structure.

These findings were confirmed in the interviews. For instance, T8 and T10 observed that ChatGPT often produces repetitive and mechanical questions, which supports the low and varied ratings for naturalness. T2 noted that although the tool has the ability to generate texts on various topics or genres or adjust content for different proficiency levels, it is heavily reliant on user input. If users do not include enough information

in the prompts, the output often fails to meet test makers' expectations. Besides, T9 supposed that this AI tool sometimes struggles to adjust the structure or simplify texts to meet specific word count limits.

Overall, the qualitative data supports the quantitative results, showing consistency in teachers' perceptions that ChatGPT can assist in creating reading test content across various aspects. However, its effectiveness was often rated as just moderate, suggesting that ChatGPT should be employed as a supportive tool rather than the sole means of test creation, as its usefulness in reading test design largely depends on how well the prompts are written.

Table 3.2.1. Teachers Evaluation of ChatGPT's Ability to Generating Reading Test Content.

	1	2	3	4	5
ChatGPT-generated questions					
Accuracy (in terms of grammar, word choice, and overall appropriateness)	0%	5%	45%	45%	5%
Naturalness	5%	10%	50%	20%	15%
Variety (regarding Skill Focus, such as factual recall, inference, vocabulary understanding, main idea identification)	0%	25%	25%	45%	5%
Variety (regarding Difficulty Levels)	0%	15%	40%	40%	5%
ChatGPT-generated texts					
Accuracy (in terms of grammar, word choice, and overall appropriateness)	0%	20%	30%	50%	0%
Naturalness	0%	5%	60%	25%	10%
Variety (regarding Genres, such as fiction, non-fiction, academic texts, practical texts)	0%	20%	60%	20%	0%
Variety (regarding Topics, such as science, history, literature, or technology)	0%	15%	50%	30%	5%
Other aspects					
ChatGPT's ability to tailor the Complexity of Texts to suit beginners, intermediate learners, or advanced learners	0%	5%	60%	30%	5%
ChatGPT's ability to tailor the length and structure of texts	5%	5%	65%	20%	5%

3.2.2. Teachers' Views on the Usefulness of ChatGPT in English Reading Test Design

As shown in Table 3.2.2., teachers generally have positive perceptions of ChatGPT's ability to create reading tests, with agreement rates ranging from 60% to 95% in most aspects. In particular, 95% of teachers (75% agreed, 20% strongly agreed) viewed ChatGPT as a helpful tool for generating reading comprehension questions. For generating texts, 60% agreed and 15% strongly agreed. Additionally, 85% (65% agreed, 20%

strongly agreed) found it effective in saving time and effort. However, only 25% believed this application could effectively reduce biases in test design, while 60% remained neutral. Similarly, opinions on its usefulness in aligning test content with 10th-grade curriculum standards were more divided, with 45% agreeing and 40% remaining neutral. This suggests that although ChatGPT can reduce teachers' workload by assisting them in performing various tasks related to reading test design (particularly useful for making reading

questions), there are some uncertainties about its effectiveness in avoiding biases and ensuring curriculum alignment.

Most interviewees expressed positive views about ChatGPT’s usefulness, which aligns with the survey data. Meanwhile, regarding ChatGPT’s ability to reduce bias in test design, many of them remained neutral, which corresponds with quantitative data in Table 3.2.2. According to T6, this is because ChatGPT’s output depends on how prompts are phrased and the data it has been

trained on, making it difficult to eliminate biases completely. Regarding its ability to generating test content aligned with 10th-grade curriculum standards, V1 and V3 supposed that the initial results made by ChatGPT were significantly more difficult than the actual English proficiency level of students at this grade; or this tool sometimes fails to generate questions according to the cognitive levels in Bloom’s Taxonomy, as noted by V9. This, in turn, leads some teachers to underestimate its effectiveness to some extent.

Table 3.2.2. Teachers’ Views on the Usefulness of ChatGPT in English Reading Test Design

	Strongly disagree	Dis-agree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Do you believe ChatGPT can assist you in designing English reading tests for grade 10th students?	0%	0%	30%	55%	15%
Do you think ChatGPT is a helpful tool in generating English reading comprehension texts?	0%	5%	20%	60%	15%
Do you think ChatGPT is a helpful tool in generating reading comprehension questions?	0%	0%	5%	75%	20%
Do you find ChatGPT useful for aligning reading texts and questions with grade 10 curriculum standards?	0%	5%	40%	45%	10%
Do you think ChatGPT-generated texts and questions can avoid biases and subjective opinions better than you as a test maker?	0%	15%	60%	20%	5%
Do you consider ChatGPT a powerful tool for saving time and effort in designing such tests?	0%	5%	10%	65%	20%

The results from both questionnaire and interview data indicate that high school teachers generally view ChatGPT as a helpful tool for creating reading test content, particularly when it comes to saving time and generating reading comprehension questions. This is supported by the conclusion of various studies, such as Ahn (2023), Kwon & Lee, Y. (2023), Shin & Lee, J. (2023), and Xiao et al. (2023), which highlights its capability to generate high-quality reading test content. In addition, ChatGPT’s advantage is also evident in its ability to create test components quickly and accurately in terms of grammar, word choice, and overall appropriateness, helping educators save time and effort. This is similar to the research results by Rivera-Rosas et al. (2024), who state that ChatGPT is 20 times faster than a teacher at creating questions.

3.3. Potential Challenges and Limitations in Using ChatGPT for Reading Test Design

Besides its advantages, using ChatGPT to design reading tests also presents challenges. These challenges stem from two main sources:

- (1) limitations in the tool’s generated content, and
- (2) difficulties that teachers face when crafting effective prompts.

As shown in Table 3.3.1, 75% of participants believed that ChatGPT still has some shortcomings in creating reading test content (50% agreed and 25% strongly agreed that such issues persist). In addition, 70% remained neutral about the relevance of the generated content to their reading test design needs, and 90% supposed that teachers must carefully check and revise the output before using it in assessments. This suggests that both the tool’s limitations and the prompting process require careful attention to ensure content quality.

According to Table 3.3.2., the proportion of agreement on the challenges that teachers might encounter when using ChatGPT for making test components is consistently high, ranging from 75% to 85%. Notably, the most significant concerns (85%) include the time-consuming process of writing prompts, the tendency for ChatGPT-generated correct answers to be by

far longer than incorrect ones, the potential biases and inaccuracies in AI-generated content, and the need for careful editing this kind of content before use. V3 and V7 stated that teachers often invest considerable effort in writing prompts as this activity is necessary to ensure the quality of ChatGPT's responses. Otherwise, the output may easily fall below the users' expectation, as reflected in the responses of 16 participants given in Table 3.3.2. Even when prompts are carefully written, the output is not always perfect. 75% of teachers claimed that ChatGPT sometimes generates output that might not match their requirements. This means that while prompt quality is crucial, there are also limitations in the AI's processing and generation abilities. For example, even when prompts were well-crafted, V9 pointed out that sentence structures in the generated reading texts are sometimes too complex for 10th-grade students. Meanwhile, V2 and V4 found that ChatGPT could create distractors that were not based on the reading passages, making correct options are more obvious to students and reducing the test's validity. V2 also mentioned that this AI tool could produce different results for the same prompts at different times. It can be seen that the problems arise not only from users' input but also from ChatGPT's current limitations as a language model. Nevertheless, V7 stayed optimistic and mentioned in the interview that it is true there are still some existing issues in ChatGPT's output, this application is further improved and limits previous errors.

Overall, the findings imply that as ChatGPT is just a supporting tool, and to reduce potential problems in its generated test content, users should carefully write prompts and check the output. V3 and V7 suggested that teachers include at least three factors in the prompts for generating passages: the topic of the passage, a word count limit, and the test takers' level of English proficiency. Moreover, to make the passages more relevant to the curriculum, teachers should require ChatGPT to create passages based on some keywords taken from the materials that students have learned in class. For questions, V6 and V8 provided tips such as asking ChatGPT to generate more questions than needed to have more choices of higher-quality ones.

The current study reveals that teachers face two major challenges when using ChatGPT

to design English reading tests: writing effective prompts and reviewing AI-generated outputs. Particularly, as a significant number of participants expressed concerns about the tool's ability to fully meet their test design requirements. For example, they were uncertain about the relevance of the generated content to their test design needs, which is almost the same as the findings of Sihite et al. (2023) – ChatGPT can produce content that aligns with the expected constructs, but only to a limited degree. Besides, the teachers noticed that ChatGPT sometimes produces mechanical or repetitive questions, which lack the natural variation found in teacher-made items; and that the tool also struggles to adjust the length and structure of a text. As a result, the generated questions are less natural than those created by teachers and are often less challenging to grade 10 students, whereas the paraphrased texts produced by the tool contain sentence structures that are too complex and exceed the learners' English proficiency level. Surprisingly, when compared to the findings from other studies, we found that teachers have highly diverse perspectives on these matters. Participants in research conducted by Xiao et al. (2023) suppose generated reading materials are suitable for students' English proficiency level and even surpass the quality of existing human-written ones, whereas, teachers in Negro's study (2024) believe these kinds of content are too difficult for secondary school students. Some educators in Nguyen's investigation (2023) do not highly value ChatGPT's generated questions, as their distractors are not difficult enough to distinguish test takers at advanced levels. Beyond previous research, we identified additional shortcomings in this tool's output, such as potential presence of biases, subjective opinions, and fabricated questions; which make a high proportion of teachers concerns these materials' reliability.

In summary, the findings suggest that to address the issues and maximize the benefits of using this application in reading test design, teachers should be trained in both prompt writing and content evaluation.

Table 3.3.1. Teachers’ Perceptions of ChatGPT’s Limitations in Reading Test Design

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Do you find ChatGPT-generated content always relevant to your reading test design needs?	0%	5%	70%	20%	5%
Do you think that ChatGPT’s shortcomings in designing reading tests still persist?	0%	0%	25%	50%	25%
Do you believe ChatGPT can replace teachers in designing reading tests for 10th-grade students?	25%	40%	25%	10%	0%
Do you agree that teachers should carefully check and revise ChatGPT-generated texts and questions before using them to assess students’ reading ability?	0%	0%	10%	20%	70%

Table 3.3.2. Teachers’ Challenges in Using ChatGPT for Reading Test Design

	Responses from participants	
	Total	Percentage
I need to spend a lot of time thinking and writing the prompt for ChatGPT to generate texts and questions suitable with students’ level.	17	85%
ChatGPT could provide results that do not match my requirements when I give instructions that lack detail and clarity.	16	80%
ChatGPT may generate texts and questions that do not align with my requirements for test objectives, word limits, or readability, even when I clearly specify them in the prompts.	15	75%
The correct option for each question created by ChatGPT is often obvious because it is much longer than the incorrect ones.	17	85%
Questions created by ChatGPT are sometimes fabricated.	15	75%
There are still potential inaccuracies or biases in ChatGPT-generated materials that make me not realize whether these materials are reliable and appropriate or not.	17	85%
I need to spend considerable time editing and modifying the content generated by ChatGPT before using it in tests.	17	85%

4. CONCLUSION

The current study emphasizes high school teachers’ perspectives on the notable strengths and weaknesses of using ChatGPT in designing 10th-grade reading tests across various aspects. While this tool offers certain conveniences, such as the quick and accurate creation of output, potential shortcomings still persist, requiring teachers to be careful when crafting prompts and to carefully review the generated content before using it in assessments. Moreover, it is suggested that, to be

more effective in employing this tool, educators should receive proper training or guidance on the utilization, which is also highlighted in the study by Kaplan-Rakowski et al. (2023) and Meniado (2023).

Although this study could offer some empirical insights into the research field, it still has certain limitations, particularly due to the small number of participants. Further research into ChatGPT’s reading test generation capabilities remains essential for future exploration.

NHẬN THỨC CỦA GIÁO VIÊN TRUNG HỌC PHỔ THÔNG VỀ VIỆC SỬ DỤNG CHATGPT TRONG VIỆC TẠO BÀI KIỂM TRA ĐỌC HIỂU TIẾNG ANH CHO HỌC SINH LỚP 10

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TÓM TẮT

Bài kiểm tra đọc hiểu là những bài kiểm tra hiệu quả để đánh giá khả năng đọc hiểu của người học tiếng Anh, tuy nhiên các giáo viên cho rằng việc tạo ra chúng thường tốn nhiều thời gian và công sức. Với sự phát triển của các công cụ AI như ChatGPT, nhiều giáo viên tiếng Anh đã tận dụng chúng để hỗ trợ họ tạo ra các bài kiểm tra này. Mặc dù ChatGPT có thể tạo ra nhiều thành phần của bài kiểm tra đọc hiểu, một số giáo viên lo ngại rằng nội dung do ChatGPT tạo ra không đáng tin cậy nếu không có sự giám sát của con người. Để tìm hiểu nhận thức của giáo viên trung học về việc sử dụng ChatGPT cho mục đích này, chúng tôi đã thực hiện đề tài bằng cách sử dụng phương pháp trộn lẫn lồng ghép. Chúng tôi đã phát bảng hỏi cho 20 giáo viên trung học quen thuộc với công cụ này; sau đó, để hiểu sâu hơn về ý kiến của họ, chúng tôi đã tiến hành phỏng vấn bán cấu trúc với 10 người tham gia được chọn ngẫu nhiên. Sau khi phân tích dữ liệu, chúng tôi nhận thấy từ 60% đến 95% giáo viên đồng ý rằng ChatGPT hữu ích trong việc tạo ra các bài kiểm tra đọc hiểu ở nhiều khía cạnh khác nhau, đặc biệt trong việc tạo ra các câu hỏi đọc hiểu (95%) và tiết kiệm thời gian và công sức (85%). Tuy nhiên, 75% người trả lời cũng cho rằng vẫn còn một số vấn đề tồn tại trong kết quả do ChatGPT tạo ra, chẳng hạn như cách diễn đạt lặp lại hoặc máy móc trong các câu hỏi, sự không nhất quán về độ dài và cấu trúc của đoạn văn, cũng như khả năng không chính xác hoặc thiên vị. Điều này làm nổi bật vai trò quan trọng của giáo viên trong việc xem xét và tinh chỉnh nội dung do AI tạo ra để đảm bảo tính phù hợp trước khi sử dụng trong các bài đánh giá.

Từ khóa: ChatGPT trong EFL/ELT, nhận thức của giáo viên tiếng Anh trung học, đánh giá năng lực tiếng Anh.

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